

**TO STUDY THE FACTORS OF MOTIVATION TO ATTEND
TRAINING UNDER PRADHAN MANTRI KAUSHAL VIKAS
YOJANA (PMKVY) AND DEEN DAYAL UPADHYAYA
GRAMEEN KAUSHALYA YOJANA (DDUGKY)**

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Abstract

The government of India has taken several initiatives for skill development among rural youth through Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY) schemes. In this context, the impact of the PMKVY and DDU-GKY initiatives of the government has to be studied as a huge sum of money is involved in the implementation of the scheme. The present study examines the factors of motivation to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDUGKY) in Jalgaon Taluka of Maharashtra state. The study concluded that the factors that motivated trainees to attend PMKVY are Secured feelings, Self-confidence, Helpful governmental schemes, Start own business, and Personal income. The top five factors that motivated trainees to attend DDUGKY are Helpful governmental schemes, Increase family income, Self-confidence, Personal income, and Start an own business.

Keywords: PMKVY, DDUGKY, Factors of Motivation, Friedman Chi-square

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I. INTRODUCTION

(Government of India, 2021) From the independence Indian government focusing on the development of rural areas. The government has introduced several schemes for rural

development in the field of health, education, farming, shelter, employment, etc. Since 2014, Government has launched many new schemes for the development of the country and the residents.

(Planning Commission report, 2016) One of the greatest challenges in India today is to achieve national development and to solve the problems of underdevelopment. The term 'rural development' suggests the overall development of the rural area to improve the quality of life of rural people. Therefore, the ministries of the Government of India have come up with various government programs called schemes or plans (Yojana) from time to time.

(Skill India, 2021) Youth is one of the most important players of the country who help in achieving rural development and economic prosperity. Therefore, our country recognizes the importance of youth in the society so that various step is taken to ensure that the workforce of tomorrow has future-ready skills. Skill India is one of the important initiatives of the Government of India. It aims to train over forty crore people in different skills by 2022 in India and is also able to create new opportunities, space, and scope of the talents of Indian Youth for self-development. In the world, India has one of the youngest population profiles with over 65% of its population below the age of 35 years.

The government of India has initiated various programs over the years like; National Skill Development Mission (NSDP), Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY), and Skill Loan Scheme, etc., under Skill India. The main objective of the national skills India development program is to employ the youth by enabling them to undertake viable economic activities. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) is primarily envisioned to enable and mobilize a large number of Indian youth to take up skill training and become employable and earn their livelihood. The initiative came into force on March 20, 2015, to increase the productivity of the existing workforce and align the training and certification to the needs of the country. The Ministry of Rural Development (MoRD) announced the Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY) Antyodaya Diwas, on 25th September 2014. DDU-GKY is a part of the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), tasked with the dual objectives of adding diversity to the incomes of rural poor families and cater to the career aspirations of rural youth.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(PMKVY, 2021) The Government of India has launched a "Skills India" program to equip

young people with skills to improve their abilities and work productivity. It offers courses across 40 sectors aligned to the industry's standards and the government, under the National Skill Qualification Framework. PMKVY is implemented by the National Skills Development Corporation (NSDC) across the country under the guidance of the Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE). The details of PMKVY centers and available vocational courses in the respective locality are available on the PMKVY website.

(Sharada Prasad Committee, 2016) Most of the PMKVY training courses are short due to the lack of knowledge of the pre-apprenticeship period by the candidate and the low admission rate (12%). The committee recommends that PMKVY pay attention to job opportunities available in the market, select suitable specialist courses at the center, and provide skills training courses relevant to the local labor market. The salary of the trained candidate is between rupees between Rs. 5,000 and 10,000, where the Committee recommends training that can offer a high wage between Rs. 40,000 and 50,000.

(Anbuthambi and Chandrasekaran, 2017) in their paper on "Impact of Skill India on Rural Youth – A Perspective" described the current context of the country's rural skills development initiative. Their paper underlines that the cost-effectiveness of skills development programs is a matter of great concern and must ensure equal opportunities for all genders and all social groups. Vocational training can help create more and more entrepreneurs in the future.

(Aggarwal, 2016) analyzed the skills development process in India from different angles. The paper highlights the need for policymakers to focus on the qualitative aspects of skills development programs rather than the quantitative ones. The current situation shows that the country needs to strengthen its cooperation with the private sector to improve the quality of ITIs and exceed the vocational training targets to improve vocational training programs.

(Okada, (2012) in his paper "Skills Development for Youth in India: Challenges and Opportunities" identified recent initiatives aimed at facilitating the transition of young people to the world of work. India faces major challenges in developing the skills of young people for several reasons. This article describes the skills gap that exists in India between what the industry needs based on recent rapid economic growth and the skills that young people have acquired through vocational training. It also suggests that India should increase its investment in education and training for young people, promote industrial development and contribute to sustainable growth.

(Rashmi, 2018) Human factors are the key to the development process. Highly skilled labor is essential for the rapid development of our economy, and for fair economic development, it is necessary to connect the majority of the rural population. India has huge geographical dividends. According to the 2011 census, India has 55 million potential workers aged 15-35 in rural areas. Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDUGKY), part of the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), was established to improve the economic situation of the poor in rural areas. It aims to meet the livelihood ambitions of young people living in rural areas by training them and offering them job opportunities. This article focuses on Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana and emphasizes its importance in increasing employment in rural Chhattisgarh.

(MISHRA & JENA, Oct-Dec 2018) The paper sought to (i) analyze DDUGKY's performance in the Keonjhar district of Orissa and (ii) analyze the economic and social impact of the DDUGKY program in the Keonjhar district of Orissa. This program will help you better understand the number of skilled rural youth and self-employed people in the Keonjhar district. According to the survey, DDUGKY is the best in the Keonjhar area. Respondents' income and costs increased after the implementation of the DDUGKY program. The study also found that those involved in industrial support trade earned more than those engaged in retail and/or sales jobs. Although this program is primarily for the benefit of the economically disadvantaged, the government must not only prevent dropouts but also implement appropriate policies to mobilize and publicize the program. Therefore, policymakers should pay attention to rational arrangements, instructor development programs, instructor and trainee salaries, and the use of the latest technology.

(Vaibhav Verma and Pradeep Singh Chauhan, 2021) Their study examines the role of Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Vikas Yojana (DDU-GKY) in the development of rural youth in the Haryana State. Secondary data (2015-2021) were used for the study. The results show that the interest of the population towards DDU-GKY and the interns recruited has greatly diminished, which is a matter of concern.

III. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of the present study is **“To study the factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDUGKY) in Jalgaon Taluka.”**

Hypothesis: PMKVY

H0: The factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana are not different in Jalgaon Taluka.

H1: The factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana are different in Jalgaon Taluka.

Hypothesis: DDUGKY

H0: The factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana are not different in Jalgaon Taluka.

H1: The factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana are different in Jalgaon Taluka.

Data collection and research instrument

Primary data is collected by administering a structured questionnaire consisting of a 7-point scale. The 200 respondents from the Jalgaon Taluka were asked to provide a level of agreement for the factors that motivated them to attend training programs under PMKVY and DDUGKY.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

To achieve the research objectives, the analysis was carried out by calculating the mean ranks, and the hypothesis was tested using the Friedman Chi-square test.

Data Analysis and Inference

Reliability analysis was carried out on the factors of motivation to attend the training programs.

Table-1 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.918	10

Cronbach's alpha showed the questionnaire reached acceptable reliability, $\alpha = 0.918$. Thus questionnaire was found to be reliable.

To test the hypothesis, the Friedman Chi-square test was used for each factor. Table 2 represents the descriptive statistics.

PMKVY**Table 2 Mean Ranks- PMKVY**

	Mean Rank
Independence	3.72
Innovativeness	3.71
Monetary benefits	4.31
Special skills	5.65
Self-confidence	6.62
Personal income	5.88
Increase family income	5.23
Start own business	5.92
Secured feeling	7.57
Helpful governmental schemes	6.42

a. Government Scheme Aailed = PMKVY

Table 3 Friedman Test

N	100
Chi-Square	229.047
df	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Government Scheme Aailed = PMKVY

b. Friedman Test

Observation: $\chi^2(9) = 229.047, p = 0.000, N=100$

Interpretation: Since the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that the factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana are different for every trainee.

DDUGKY**Table 4 Mean Ranks- DDUGKY**

	Mean Rank
Independence	4.29
Innovativeness	4.31
Monetary benefits	3.78
Special skills	4.79
Self-confidence	6.53
Personal income	6.39
Increase family income	6.83
Start own business	6.03
Secured feeling	4.31
Helpful governmental schemes	7.76

a. Government Scheme Aailed = DDUGKY

Table 4 Friedman Test

N	100
Chi-Square	236.334
df	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000

a. Government Scheme Aailed = DDUGKY

b. Friedman Test

Observation: $\chi^2 (9) = 236.334, p = 0.000, N=210$

Interpretation: Since the p-value (0.000) is less than the level of significance (0.05) the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is concluded that the factors that motivated the trainees to attend training under Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana are different for every trainee.

v. CONCLUSION

The government of India has taken several initiatives for skill development among rural youth

through Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY) schemes. This paper has studied the factors of motivation to attend training under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDUGKY) in the Jalgaon Taluka region of Maharashtra, India.

The top five factors that motivated trainees to attend PMKVY are Secured feeling (Mean Rank 7.57), Self-confidence (Mean Rank 6.62), Helpful governmental schemes (Mean Rank 6.42), Start own business (Mean Rank 5.92), and Personal income (Mean Rank 5.88).

The top five factors that motivated trainees to attend DDUGKY are Helpful governmental schemes (Mean Rank 7.76), Increase family income (Mean Rank 6.83), Self-confidence (Mean Rank 6.53), Personal income (Mean Rank 6.39), and Start own business (Mean Rank 6.03).

Thus, it is concluded that the factors that motivated trainees to attend PMKVY and DDUGKY are different.

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